

Challenges Faced by Individuals with Chronic Morbidity to Avail Healthcare Services during COVID-19 Pandemic – A Qualitative Study in a Village of West Bengal

Sayantani Nayak¹, Rupali P Thakur², Pranita Taraphdar³, Pramit Goswami⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College

²Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College

³Professor and Head, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College

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Corresponding author: Dr. Pramit Goswami

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Abstract

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic has posed unprecedented challenges and threats to the health care system, particularly affecting the management of chronic morbidity patients especially in rural areas. This study aims to explore the difficulties and constraints faced by the individuals with chronic morbidity, towards health seeking behavior, residing in the study area, due to Covid19 pandemic.

Methodology: Qualitative exploratory design employing semi-structured interviews was adapted for the study. The interviews were conducted using in-depth interview of by individuals with chronic morbidity to avail healthcare services, residing in a village of West Bengal, due to Covid19 Pandemic. Inductive analysis of in-depth interview was undertaken to determine themes, categories and codes.

Results: The findings of this research are: (i) Unable to avail healthcare facility (ii) Availability of health care services at increased cost (iii) Reduced earnings and decreased capacity to pay (iv) Fear of 'Corona infection' (v) Lack of proper information.

Conclusion: The study explores that mere availability of doctor consultation is not sufficient for continuation of care; transport facilities, availability of drugs all play their part. Community participation for facilitating these patients were also scarce, especially in a setting where the prevalence of NCDs and proportion of elderly population are high.

Keywords: COVID-19, Chronic morbidity, Healthcare access, Pandemic, SARS-CoV-2.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic had thrown a major challenge to the world since November 2019 [1]. WHO on recognizing the rapid spread of COVID-19 and the threats it poses, had declared it as an international public health emergency on 30 January 2020. Public health measures such as partial or full restriction and lockdown was implemented, from time to time, to curb the transmission all over the world, including India [2]. In these unprecedented times of pandemic, the health seeking behaviour of the common public was affected, since most of the people depended on public transport for accessing the healthcare facilities [3]. This had resulted in much difficulties to access routine as well as emergency health services. People who suffered from chronic diseases like hypertension, diabetes, chronic kidney disease, cardiovascular disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and malignancy suffered the

most and had much higher risk of adverse outcome than their counterparts without any chronic disease [4]. Furthermore, data revealed that the presence of two or more conditions (multimorbidity) accentuated the outcomes in COVID-19 with around 10-fold risk [5,6]. In a developing country like India, the social determinants of health intensified the sufferings of pandemic such as poverty, social inequality, affordability as well as accessibility of healthcare services [7]. Again, during these very times, the healthcare delivery system in a developing country like India came under stress to control the novel virus which in turn hampered its ongoing healthcare service delivery [8]. New strategies to mitigate this need of the unprecedented challenge led to more focus on containment, screening and critical care management of Covid19 cases than routine curative and preventive management of already existing disease and emergency care [9]. A

rapid global survey conducted by the World Health Organization (WHO) to assess Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) management during COVID-19 found NCD services to be impacted, especially in low-and middle-income countries (LMICs) [10]. There is exacerbation of outcome of Covid 19 due to social and health inequalities already present in our society. [11] In order to address the issues of management of chronic morbidities amidst pandemic in villages of India, a better understanding of the challenges faced, from their personal experiences, in low resource setting was needed. In the above background a qualitative study was conducted on patients suffering from chronic diseases in a village of Purba Bardhaman district, West Bengal to explore their difficulties, needs and challenges, during the Covid 19 pandemic towards health care seeking needs.

Materials and Methods

Study design, setting, and duration: This community-based cross-sectional Qualitative study was conducted in Kachgodia, a village under Bhatar CD block of Purba Bardhaman district, West Bengal between February 2021 and August 2021.

Study Population: Adult chronic morbidity patients who were taking daily medication for at least 6 months, residing in the study area for more than 6 months, were the study population. Study subjects not willing to participate in the study and Study subjects who are critically ill were excluded.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique: A list of eligible subjects was prepared with the help of ASHA and other village volunteers. Identified subject from that list were visited and interviewed at their home. Sample size was determined by data saturation and data exhaustion as it indicated by simultaneous analysis of data.

Data collection, tools, and technique: Upon giving consent, the data was collected through in-depth interviews using a pre-designed pre-tested IDI guide consisting of questions regarding nature of morbidity, care seeking behavior and compliance to treatment among them, as well as questions to explore the difficulties and constraints faced by the individuals with chronic morbidity residing in the study area, due to Covid-19 pandemic.

The response was recorded as well. Appropriate documents related to their morbidity like prescription, investigation reports and other relevant documents were reviewed. Data analysis was done simultaneously with the data collection. IDIs were stopped once Data saturation was achieved.

Data analysis: The inductive thematic analysis approach has been utilized for data analysis. The difficulties and experience of the chronic morbidity patient were interviewed by in-depth interview (IDI)

method. The initial audio files of interviews were listened and transcribed in English into verbatim and then read several times to gain a general impression. The resulting text from the interviews were read line-by-line and broken down into meaningful units (words or sentence or paragraphs), which was then be condensed, abstracted, coded, and labelled.

The data of the IDIs were transcribed in Bengali and back to English. Finally, the transcribed data was thematically analysed and summarized. Data analysis revealed codes which were categorized into subthemes. The subthemes were analysed to determine emergent themes, regarding the experiences of the study subjects. Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Burdwan Medical College & Hospital, Purba Bardhaman. Participation of the subjects in the study was voluntary & informed consent were obtained from all participants. Confidentiality and anonymity of information was maintained.

Results

Through inductive approach the study explored the difficulties and constraints faced by individuals with chronic morbidity to avail healthcare services, residing in a village of West Bengal, due to Covid-19 Pandemic. Thirteen chronic morbidity patients were interviewed in depth for this study, till there was data saturation on simultaneous analysis. Of them, eight were male and five were females. Participants were found to be suffering for on an average of 6 years, ranging between 1 and 17 years and the most common chronic morbidity was hypertension. Majority of the participants mentioned about facing some difficulties. Although their perceptions about the level of difficulties varied, most reported that investigations and availability of medicine were the most affected areas of health care delivery.

This community mainly availed the government block healthcare at Bhatar, an outreach rural clinic at Kachgodia village of Bhatar block, run by Community medicine department of Burdwan medical college and Burdwan medical college for consultation, medicines and investigations. People suffered a lot during total lockdown period than restriction phase. No transport services were available for a few months. Specialty healthcare services at local level were not available, only general healthcare services were available but with limited logistics. Private healthcare services were sometimes available but at higher cost and with restricted timings. Apart from that the lockdown also affected their source of income which indirectly affected their access to healthcare. Sometimes the fear of covid-19 infection also led them to not go to healthcare facility when needed. Again, lack of information regarding Telemedicine / e-OPD

services acted as a constraint towards availing free services.

Figure-1: Fishbone diagram showing Difficulties and constraints faced by individuals with chronic morbidity to avail healthcare services, residing in a village of West Bengal, due to Covid19 Pandemic. Emergent Themes

Five broad emergent themes were revealed after analysis of transcribed data. The themes were:

Unable to avail healthcare facility

- **Temporary unavailability of Government healthcare services:**

The Government healthcare services were available throughout the pandemic except rural outreach clinic which was closed temporarily for almost 2 months. Apart from that other government healthcare services at block and district level were available to the rural residents. This made many unable to avail the healthcare services because many were used to the local health clinic due to distance and convenience. As one of the interviewees said, “I am an old man. I generally visit the rural health center. I don’t prefer going to hospitals because I can’t stand in queue for so long and someone has to accompany me. So, when the rural health center was closed, I had to avail the private clinic.”

- **Unavailability of specialty healthcare at local level:**

Consultation for minor health issues were available at the local level but for specialty advice they were dependent on Burdwan medical college or even other Government healthcare specialty at greater distance. Like some of the participants said “At first, I had gone to Burdwan medical college & hospital for my vision disturbance where on work up, my

hypertension was also diagnosed. My eyesight problem was as a consequence of hypertension. I took medicines for both and went for regular check-up. I was referred to Kolkata for my eye check-up too, where I visited once. But then, after lockdown my treatment was hampered. I couldn’t go so far. I had continued the same medication for months and once or twice had gone for blood pressure measurement.

On relaxation of restriction, I again went to Burdwan medical college for treatment.” This issue was applicable to many disciplines, like another participant stated “.... apart from that I had to wait for my cardiac follow up. I was feeling very uneasiness in chest for few days but had to wait for cardiac consultation. Even my diabetes medications were continued without tests for long before I could get tests done.”

- **Unavailability of transport**

During first phase of lockdown and also during initial phases of restriction there was unavailability of transport for long distance. Though vehicles for short distance travel was available. So, the people who had earlier visited doctors at medical colleges or at city couldn’t go for follow up. As stated by one, “I didn’t get bus like before to go to the city to visit medical college. I have taken trekker but it was very uncomfortable, and I restrained going any further. “Whereas another participant said, “I used to take

bus, now during lockdown, I go to the nearby Bhatar hospital by TOTO”.

- **Unavailability of accompanying persons/ caretaker**

Some of the participants were old and stayed alone and they needed a caretaker or someone to accompany them to hospital or buy their medicines. During Covid19 pandemic, there was severe scarcity of accompanying person. Like one of them said, “I was not able to take medicines when my medicines got finished for 14 days. A neighbor’s son got my medicines from Bhatar hospitals but all of them were not available.”

Availability of health care services at increased cost

- **Availability of transportation at higher cost**

Even if transportation was made available or arranged during emergency, it was always at a higher cost and that was expenses added to the actual healthcare cost. This was mentioned by a participant, “According to another participant “Earlier I used to go to the city for consulting a gynae doctor and also got my medicines and tests done there for free. Now as public transportation was not there and private transportation was costly, also the BPHC didn’t provide all the medicines during lockdown, so I had to buy from private pharmacy.”

- **Availability of Private healthcare services at higher cost**

The private healthcare facilities were available during the pandemic but with a lesser frequency and duration. The private clinic consultation fee, medicines and investigations costed out of pocket expenditure. Like mentioned by one of the interviewees, “Once I had been very sick due to my high sugar level which was due to irregularity of my medicine intake. My son took me to a private clinic nearby. The doctor also visits the clinic sometimes and not on regular basis. So, I had to wait. When he saw my sugar level, he called for few more blood tests. I had it done at the private facility far from here. So, It was cumbersome and also needed much money.”

Reduced earnings and decreased capacity to pay

- **Unavailability of work/ source of income:**

Most of the participants mentioned about their weak financial situation during lockdown. Like one of them said, “We are poor people. My husband works at fields, so buying and traveling was a burden on us.” Some mentioned about unavailability of work, whereas some mentioned about lesser pay at work. “I don’t earn. It was very difficult. All the medicines were also bought by my son and I had taken them regularly after that. “Some mentioned about reduced

payment during lockdown too, “We are poor people and my son was without work for few months during complete lockdown. After that too he got less payment at the shop he works for. “Another one said that, “My son is a toto driver, so during lockdown there was less income and that was a biggest problem.”

- **Unavailability of financial supporter:**

Most participants were in their old age who needed someone to financially support them Due to lockdown many families were apart from their care “...I suffered of weakness and also had less money. My daughter is married off far, she was very worried about us. She sometimes helps us with money. She can’t visit us for many months now. Definitely it was very difficult on us.”

Fear of ‘Corona infection’

- **Fear of ‘Corona infection’ from healthcare facilities**

Participants mentioned they were very worried and are not willing to go to health facilities even if they have general health problems. They either continue pre-prescribed medicines or took advice from local pharmacists or self-medication on minor health issues but they were not willing to visit any health centres due to fear of getting COVID-19 from health workers. As said by one of the participants, “: I was unable to go for follow up so frequently like before. Rather I had to depend on the prescribed medicines. I had fear of getting the infection by visiting clinics and hospitals. My visits and blood pressure measurement were not done. I depended on prescribed drugs and had ignored trivial sicknesses like getting cold or knee pain.”

- **Fear of getting stigmatized as COVID infected**

There was an omnipresence of panic of getting the infection or worrying for family member who goes out to earn for the family. Like said by an interviewee, “I generally stay home. But my son goes out for work and I keep worrying for him, if he gets the infection.

“Even minor cough and cold or fever brought much anxiety and due to the stigma attached to COVID-19 which prompted them to conceal the disease. Some avoided visiting hospitals and got help from pharmacists, like they mentioned, “I once developed flu like fever but I got the medicines at pharmacy without seeing a doctor. “This is because, if they went to a hospital, they would be told to get the test done for Covid19 and if positive, they will be avoided and treated differently by the healthcare and the community they live in.

- **Lack of proper information**

Majority of the interviewees were unaware of the telemedicine/ e-OPD services provided by the State Government 24*7 for the special Pandemic situation during second wave. One of them said on asking whether he availed telemedicine/ e-OPD services, "No, I was not aware of such facility.". Few knew about it but didn't avail due to unavailability of proper complete information about it. Again, another one of them said, "Yes, but didn't avail it due to unavailability of proper information."

Discussions

This study has explored community perceptions of chronic morbidity patients and their experiences related to health services utilization during the COVID-19 pandemic in a rural area of West Bengal, India. Using an exploratory qualitative research model to find out the health care utilization, this study found that the COVID-[19] pandemic has acted as a torchlight to highlight the weaknesses of the present health care system. Health services utilization was found to be affected by availability, accessibility and affordability of health services of the community equally. While there was unavailability of specialty healthcare at local level, or general healthcare services with limited logistics, or incomplete information about telemedicine / e-OPD services or even transport for long distance travel, there was also financial crisis to afford the services from private facilities at local level when needed.

With regard to normal routine care (prior to COVID-19 pandemic) for their chronic illnesses, they had been visiting Government block hospital for doctor's consultation. They availed Government outreach rural clinic facilities mainly due to free supply of medicines. The specialty healthcare consultation was sought at the tertiary government health centre. During lockdown the Government rural healthcare was temporarily closed for almost 2 months. This led to unavailability of their free medicines and even at block level there was limited logistics for general healthcare requirement. The access to specialty healthcare were hindered due to disruption of transportation as well as fear attached to going to hospitals and getting the Covid19 infection in return. The fear, anxiety and social stigma attached to Covid19 also restricted them to avail the health care facility. Relevant studies point out similar findings with our study. [12,13] A study on low and middle income countries and noncommunicable disease management during Covid19 pandemic pointed out lack of affordable and quality healthcare services, lack of access to information technology and transportation. [12] Another study mentions that disruptions in routine management for chronic conditions were notably observed in individuals with chronic morbidity than

those with acute condition across the care spectrum. [13] Several previous studies have also highlighted that lockdown and transportation closures have led to not being able to attend the health services. [12] They also stated that doctor's consultation was the most challenging part for specialty treatment among the multimorbidity group. This is also true for our study except that it was more for specialty healthcare consultation. Apart from that availability of free services and medicines were the other issues added to it.

According to another study, the governments leveraged on already existing tele-medical system, and started tele-medical oversight by physicians thereby reducing physical visits to facility [14]. This was not utilised by the community because of lack of awareness as well as improper dispersion of information. Most participants shared their experience of being worried and anxious about COVID-19 and reported a lack of awareness, misinformation, and stigma as major factors contributing to the spread of COVID-19. [15]

Limitations: Limitation of this study is that the situations of localities may differ based on region, demographic characteristics like their occupation, education and awareness, household responsibilities and socio-economic status which were not explored in this study, thus possessing restricted scope of generalizability. Moreover, it is likely that the community perceptions towards health services utilization may vary with the relaxation of the lockdown and after the pandemic.

Conclusion

The study can be concluded as though there was public fear and anxiety of COVID-19, transportation disruptions, unavailability of medicines and specialty health services at local health facilities, there was participation of Private Doctors to tackle this gap. Still there was out of pocket expenditure attached to it. Therefore, the study brought out the sectors that needs to paid attention like specialty healthcare services at local level, even if with definite days of the week, Strengthening the logistics of both general and Covid19 pandemic related services and proper distribution of information of online services. However, the results of this study can be utilized for future policy and program planning to deliver effective health services during disasters and health emergencies like pandemic, in a developing country like India.

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